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Effect of Loop Length Variation in a Plain Circular Knitting Machine on the Properties of Plain Single Jersey Fabric

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ABSTRACT

The study focuses on stitch length variation in the weft-knitted fabrics to the fabric properties like air permeability, bursting strength, tightness, and geometry due to its divergence. The yarn of 30 Ne of 100% cotton fiber, 22 Ne of 80% polyester and 20% cotton (PC) blend, and 28 Ne of 76% cotton and 24% polyester (CVC) are used for the study. Fabric is produced with the same stitch length and necessary parameters are tested in the dry state and relaxed state after relaxation in standard conditions. This study supports that stitch length variation of single jersey weft knitted fabric influences GSM, values of geometric constants at the relaxed state and bursting strength positively, dimensional change, air permeability, and tightness of the fabric negatively.

Keywords

Stitch length, Air Permeability, Bursting strength, Single Jersey, Geometric Constants

Introduction

Dimensional characteristics of weft knitted fabrics are directly related to loop length to a great extent [1] [2]. Fabrics properties are also influenced by fibers and yarn properties, machine variables, processing, and finishing treatments. Yarn fineness and coarseness affect shrinkage, tightness, and the influence loop length, loop shape factor, air permeability, bursting strength, etc. [3].

Large stitch length makes the fabric more elastic, lighter with low bursting strength and high air permeability due to its low cover opacity. Fluctuation in yarn and machine variable changes yarn friction, tension at knitting point, although set to specific stitch length. Thus, fabric geometry may vary due to change in the fiber and yarn properties [4].

The patterns of stitches are changed according to the gauge of the machine in a fabric. Fabric thickness also changed due to machine gauge with same yarn diameter. Identical to the gsm of the fabrics. Generally, lower

needle gauge, mid-gauge, standard gauge, and fine gauge are used for bulkier, light, sock, and lace weight yarn [5]. However, the bursting strength of the treated fabric severely deteriorates by application of such [10]. In such cases, a balance must be maintained to attain optimal dimensional stability with minimum loss in bursting strength [11]. Hence, fabric softening agents' application becomes a necessity that helps retain the fabric strength [12]. The introduction of compact yarn instead of ring yarn was also tried [13] [14].

It is also reported that higher breaking strength for fabrics with higher than lower fabric count [15]. But one study found no relationship between bursting strength and extension. Other fibers like modal and bamboo had higher bursting strength than cotton [16]. But the knit structure could impact bursting strength [17]. It is mentioned that higher breaking strength and lower tearing strength are yielded from higher fabric counts [15]. An inverse relation between extension and strength is found. An increase in strength results in a decrease in elongation [18] [19]. The bursting strengths of single jersey, lacoste, and double pique are studied. Their findings revealed that bursting strength was highest for 'single Lacoste' and lowest for double pique knit [20]. Another report says jersey, rib, and interlock knits made from compact yarns had higher bursting strength, elongation, and pilling resistance than those made from ring-spun yarns [21]. Compact yarns had higher bursting strength and lower pilling [22]. An increase in Lycra amount also improves the bursting strength [23]. There are relationships of strength with gsm and fabric thickness; and elongations with elastane content [24] [25].

Interchangeably stretch, and elasticity terms have been used [26]. The critical loop dimensions are stitch length, length, the width of the loop, the machine gauge, needle type, cam-type, yarn feeding system, the number of feeders, takedown system, cloth rolling or spreading, monitoring, and control courses, etc. These influence dimensional properties.

The properties of weft knitted fabrics depend on the parameters set in the machines. Due to its poor dimensional stability, many experiments have established the required parameters in the machine to limit the variation and get the desired characteristics in the finished fabrics. According to the yarn shape and yarn path, different fabric structures can be produced. So, the fabric properties like grams per square meter (GSM), grey diameter, finished width, spirality, and shrinkage vary due to those machine parameters. Research to investigate the effect of different knitting parameters on knitted fabrics' physical and mechanical properties is also performed.

This study's main objective is to find out the changes due to the changes of loop length for different yarn types with the same machine gauge and diameters after dry relaxation and wet relaxation. Most of the experiments are based on after finishing stage. In this regard, this experiment aims to determine the changes in the dry state so that the intermediate modifications are also observed.

Though the dry state changes depending on the yarn's tension in the machine, it is relaxed only to get its original pressure after robing back of the loops in knitting. After finishing, other changes also occur like fiber loss, dimensional properties, yarn count, chemical effect in some cases are responsible for the property

changes of the fabrics.

This experiment has great importance to know these effects with the changes in loop length. These may open the other research area in this field after the analysis of the obtained results. Though this experiment is done in the laboratory environment on a small scale, the industrial environment's result should also be studied to reach an extensive conclusion.

For the study, three types of yarn, i.e., 100% Cotton, PC, and CVC are used to produce material using the same stitch length and machine parameters and then tested in dry and relaxed conditions. Finally, plotting these values against loop length, the effect of its variation is observed.

Methodology

A. Methods

This research is designed to study the effect of loop length on single jersey knitted fabrics' properties by collecting different data from samples produced in the same circular knitting machine using the same machine parameters. The methods for this work are listed below.

- Produce fabric with different stitch lengths by changing VDQ pulley and keep these changes the same for other yarn selected.
- Produce knitted fabrics from the three different stitch lengths.
- Collecting data from the produced fabrics like loop length, geometric constant at a dry and relaxed state, loop shape factor, air permeability, bursting strength, tightness factor, and dimensional changes by carrying out proper testing.
- Analyze the results obtained from testing using the graphical method

Yarn from the same lot is placed carefully on creels. Then, the samples were dried in relaxed condition & then processed. Testing conditioning is 65% relative humidity & $30^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a dry state. The following tests were carried out at $27^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ & 65% RH. Parameters required for a relaxed state are done before wash and after washing. Thus, geometric constants are considered for both dry and relaxed states.

B. Materials

30 Ne of 100% cotton fiber, 22 Ne of 80% polyester and 20% cotton (PC) blend, and 28 Ne of 76% cotton and 24% polyester (CVC) yarns are taken as raw material to produce weft-knitted plain fabrics using single jersey knitting machine (Orizio). Gauge, diameter, and no. of feeder were 24E, 21 inches, and 63, respectively. In this study, 9 samples of weft knitted fabrics have been produced using different stitch lengths of 2.95 mm, 2.85 mm and 2.75 mm in the same machine setting using above mentioned yarns taken in this study. The final produced fabrics are examined to determine the samples' parameters. In this research, the fabrics produced to be studied are single jersey knitted fabrics produced from three different stitch lengths. The sample fabrics are produced with one roll of fabrics from each stitch length and 1.5 meters of fabrics are taken from each type to be tested.

C. Standards and Equipment

Here, correlation and regression analysis are used to find the influences of parameters of the weft-knitted fabrics on the bursting strength. And following the regression model is to fit the experiments.

Table-I: STANDARDS USED IN THIS STUDY

Serial No	Parameters	Unit	Standard Used	Instrument Used
1	Stitch length	mm	-	cm Scale
2	Yarn count	Ne	ASTM D 2260-96	-
3	Stitch density	Per cm ²	ASTM D 3887-2008	Counting glass
4	GSM	gm/m ²	ASTM D 3776	GSM Cutter
5	Shrinkage	%	ASTM D 7983	Shrinkage Measurement Scale
6	Bursting Strength	kg/cm ²	ASTM D 6797-2015, IS 1963: 1982	Digiburst Bursting Tester.
7	Air Permeability	cc/sec/cm ²	ASTM D 737-96	MAG Air Permeability Tester

Result and Discussion

A. Effect on Fabric Weight (GSM)

When stitch length increased, the WPI, CPI, stitch density, loop shape factor, Changed correspondingly. GSM depends on knit structure, yarn count & dimensional properties of knit fabrics. When fabrics density is more, fabrics, weight is also more. Fig. 1 shows that fabric GSM increases with the increase of stitch length for 100% cotton, PC blend (80%P and20%C), and CVC (76%C and 24%P). Though yarn count is different, and the same loop lengths have used all types of fabrics shows a similar result in fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Effect on GSM

B. Effect on Dimensional Change Length Wise and Width Wise

Fig. 2 found that fabric dimensional change length wise decreases with the increase of stitch length for 100% cotton and PC blend (80%P and 20%C). But, CVC (76%C and 24%P) shows different from them. Hence, with the fabric structure's geometry, this change may vary for different types of fabrics.

Fig. 2. Effect on Dimensional Change% Length Wise

Fig. 3 found that fabric dimensional change width wise decreases with the increase of stitch length for PC blend (80%P and 20%C), and CVC (76%C and 24%P). But 100% cotton shows different from them.

Fig. 3. Effect on Dimensional Change% Width Wise

Hence, with the fabric structure's geometry, this change may vary for different types of fabrics.

C. Effect on Geometric Constant at Dry State (K_c , K_w , R)

Fig. 4-6 found that geometric constants at dry state change significantly with the change of loop length. K_c , K_w , and R all decrease with the increase of loop length for PC (80%P and 20%C) fabrics. K_c and K_w increase while R decreases with the rise of loop length for 100% Cotton fabric. K_c and R decrease while K_w increases with the increase of loop length for CVC (76%C and 24%P) fabric. Though K_c and K_w do not change similarly for all types of fabrics, loop shape factors decrease with the increase of the loop length, indicating that the tightness of the fabric reduces.

Fig.4. Effect on Geometric Constant, K_c at Dry State

Fig. 5. Effect on Geometric Constant, K_w at Dry State

Fig. 6. Effect on Geometric Constant, R at Dry State

D. Effect on Geometric Constant at Relaxed State (K_c , K_w , R)

Fig. 7-9 shows that geometric constants at a relaxed state change significantly with the change of loop length. K_c , K_w , and R all increase with the increase of loop length for 100% Cotton, PC (80%P and 20%C), and CVC (76%C and 24%P) fabrics. Thus, loop shape factors remain almost neutral with the increase of the loop length that indicates that the fabrics' tightness does not change significantly with the rise of the loop length.

Fig. 7. Effect on Geometric Constant, K_c at Relaxed State

Fig. 8. Effect on Geometric Constant, K_w at Relaxed State

Fig. 9. Effect on Geometric Constant, R at Relaxed State

E. Effect on CPCm, WPCm and SPCm at Dry State

Plotting the values of CPCm at dry state against $1/l$ and finding its slope gives K_c 's value at dry state. It is found that CPCm is directly proportional to the value of $1/l$. With the increase of the loop length, the CPCm decrease for all types of fabrics at dry state.

By putting the values of WPCm against $1/l$ and finding its slope, it gives the value of K_w . It is found that WPCm is indirectly proportional to the value of $1/l$ for both 100% cotton and CVC (76%C and 24%P) fabrics.

Whereas directly proportional for PC (80% P and 20% C) fabrics. That means, with the increase of the loop length, the WPCm increases for both 100% cotton and CVC (76%C and 24%P) fabrics but decreases for PC (80% P and 20% C) fabrics at dry state.

Putting the values of SPCm against $1/l^2$ and finding its slope gives the value of Ks. The SPCm is indirectly proportional to the value of $1/l^2$ for both 100% cotton and CVC (76%C and 24%P) fabrics. Whereas directly proportional for PC (80% P and 20% C) fabrics. With the increase of the loop length, the SPCm increases for both 100% cotton and CVC (76%C and 24%P) fabrics but slightly decreases for PC (80% P and 20% C) fabrics dry state.

F. Effect on CPCm, WPCm, and SPCm at Relaxed State

It is found that CPCm is indirectly proportional to the value of $1/l$. With the increase of the loop length, the CPCm increases for all types of fabrics at a relaxed state.

And the WPCm is indirectly proportional to the value of $1/l$. With the increase of the loop length, the WPCm increases for all types of fabrics at a relaxed state.

The SPCm is indirectly proportional to the value of $1/l^2$. With the increase of the loop length, the WPCm increases for all types of fabrics at a relaxed state.

G. Effect on Air Permeability (cc/sec/cm²)

Air permeability is dependent on loop length and fiber types, and construction of the fabric. Fig. 10 found that with the increase of loop length, the air permeability of the fabric is decreased

Fig. 10. Effect on Air Permeability

H. Effect on Bursting Strength (kg/cm²)

Bursting strength is also dependent on loop length and fiber types, and construction of the fabric. Fig. 11 found that with the increase of loop length, the bursting strength of the fabric is decreased. The resistance towards the force is more in case of less stitch length of fabric, which is why more loops per unit area.

Fig. 11. Effect on Bursting Strength

I. Effect on Tightness Factor

The tightness factor is dependent on the yarn count and loop length of the fabric. Fig. 12 found that with the increase of loop length, the tightness of the fabric is also decreased.

Fig. 12. Effect on tightness factor

Conclusion

Stitch or loop length is the primary control unit for all the properties of weft knitted fabrics. All the dimensional, comfort, handle, and other properties are affected mainly by stitch length and knit structure. GSM increases with the increase of loop length in this experiment, which is caused due to not changing the other machine setting with yarn count. Thus, yarn accumulation per square inch of the fabric is more at relaxed state which is exception in this experimental study. Lengthwise and width wise dimensional changes vary with the evolution of loop length. Length and width decrease with the rise of loop length except for CVC and 100%, respectively. In a relaxed state, all geometric constant is increased with the increase of loop length. They show different results in a dry form that is not stable after withdrawal from the knitting machines. The straight line slope by plotting

CPCm against $1/l$, WPCm against $1/l$, and SPCm against $1/l^2$ also supports the same results. Finally, air permeability and tightness factor show that they change negatively with the increase of loop length, and bursting strength increases with the rise of loop length.

Further experiments are welcome here to understand the variety of changes that influences the fabric characteristics. Especially in the dry state, the properties change differently from the relaxed state, which is the limitation of this study. As machine parameters are remained the same, due to the change of fiber characteristics and the yarn tension set during production in the machines, this may influence the result.

Table-II: EXPERIMENTAL DATA TABLE

Fabric type	VDQ pulley Value	Loop length (mm)	Yarn Count (Ne)	Geometric Constant at Dry State			Geometric Constant at Relaxed State			GSM	Air Permeability (cc/sec/cm ²)	Bursting strength (kg/cm ²)	Dimensional Change%		
				Kc	Kw	R=Kc/Kw	Kc	Kw	R=Kc/Kw				Length	Width	
100% cotton	1	120	2.95	30	2.20	1.51	1.46	2.47	1.67	1.48	157	139.6	3.94	-0.11	-0.13
	2	115	2.85		2.23	1.36	1.64	2.26	1.55	1.45	155	146.5	3.06	-0.11	-0.13
	3	110	2.75		2.14	1.30	1.64	2.14	1.46	1.47	148	156.9	1.97	-0.07	-0.16
80% Polyester and 20% Cotton	1	120	2.95	22	2.10	1.32	1.60	2.42	1.49	1.63	186	118.8	4.81	-0.03	-0.03
	2	115	2.85		2.12	1.33	1.59	2.16	1.40	1.55	173	132.6	3.61	-0.03	0.00
	3	110	2.75		2.17	1.33	1.63	2.00	1.25	1.60	160	160.4	3.06	-0.02	0.01
76% Cotton	1	120	2.95	28	2.19	1.45	1.51	2.49	1.73	1.44	160	136.1	3.5	-0.03	-0.19
	2	115	2.85		2.31	1.32	1.75	2.09	1.63	1.29	155	143.1	2.5	-0.07	-0.14
	3	110	2.75		2.29	1.20	1.91	1.92	1.47	1.31	147	150.0	2.08	-0.06	-0.08

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